

PROBLEMS OF ARCHITECTURE AND CONSTRUCTION

Scientific and technical journal

e-ISSN: 2901-7845 (ISSN: 2091-5004)

2025, VOLUME-03, ISSUE-04.

The journal is included in the list of scientific journals in which scientific articles on technical sciences (construction, mechanics and machine building) and architecture are subject to publication by the decision of the OAK Board (certificate No. 00757. 2000.31.01). It is hereby notified that the articles published in English in our journal are equated to scientific articles published in foreign scientific publications in accordance with the decision of the OAK

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MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND INNOVATIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF
UZBEKISTAN

Samarkand State Architecture and Construction University,
Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

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ПРОБЛЕМЫ АРХИТЕКТУРЫ И СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВА
(научно-технический журнал) 2025, ТОМ 3, ВЫПУСК 45383.

ME'MORCHILIK VA QURILISH MUAMMOLARI
, 2025, 3-JILD, 4-SON,

ISSN: 2091-5004, e-ISSN:2901-7845

<https://portal.issn.org/resource/ISSN/2091-5004>

Samarkand, 2025

THE PROPAGATION OF SEISMIC WAVES IN THE SUBTERRANEAN AQUIFERS DURING TRAIN TRANSIT.

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Abstract. This paper presents a three-dimensional numerical study of ground vibration propagation induced by railway train movement. The dynamic load generated by a moving freight train is modeled as a time-dependent force acting on the track structure. The problem is solved using the finite element method with irregular tetrahedral elements to accurately represent the soil domain. The influence of key physical and mechanical soil parameters on vibration intensity is investigated. Ground vibration responses are evaluated at various distances from the railway track to assess attenuation characteristics.

Keywords: railway transport, ground vibration, finite element analysis, soil dynamics, elasticity theory, boundary conditions, wave velocity.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada temir yo'l poezdi harakati natijasida yuzaga keladigan yer vibratsiyalarining uch o'lchovli raqamli tadqiqoti taqdim etilgan. Harakatlanuvchi yuk poezdi tomonidan hosil qilingan dinamik yuk, yo'l inshootiga ta'sir etuvchi vaqtga bog'liq kuch sifatida modellashirilgan. Masala tuproq maydonini aniq ifodalash uchun noaniq tetraedral elementlardan foydalangan holda tugallangan elementlar usuli yordamida yechilgan. Vibratsiya intensivligiga ta'sir qiluvchi asosiy fizik va mexanik tuproq parametrlarining ta'siri o'rganilgan. Yer vibratsiyalari temir yo'l izidan turli masofalardagi nuqtalarda baholangan va attenuatsiya xususiyatlari aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: temir yo'l transporti, tuproq vibratsiyalari, elementlar usuli bo'yicha tahlil, tuproq dinamikasi, elastiklik nazariyasi, chegaraviy shartlar, to'lqin tezligi.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлен трёхмерный численный анализ распространения вибраций грунта, вызванных движением железнодорожного поезда. Динамическая нагрузка, создаваемая движущимся грузовым поездом, моделируется как зависящая от времени сила, действующая на конструкцию пути. Задача решена с использованием метода конечных элементов с неравномерными тетраэдральными элементами для точного представления области грунта. Исследуется влияние ключевых физических и механических параметров грунта на интенсивность вибраций. Реакции грунта на вибрации оцениваются на различных расстояниях от железнодорожного пути для анализа характеристик затухания.

Ключевые слова: железнодорожный транспорт, вибрации в грунте, анализ методом конечных элементов, динамика грунта, теория упругости, граничные условия, скорость распространения волн.

Introduction.

Vibrations and noise generated by transport systems, particularly railway traffic, often exceed permissible sanitary standards and pose a potential risk to nearby buildings and infrastructure. Numerous experimental observations and field surveys confirm that this issue remains relevant, especially in densely populated areas.

Since soil acts as a transmitting medium for vibration energy from the source to surrounding structures, understanding the mechanical behavior of ground materials is

essential for reliable vibration assessment. Vibrations propagating through near-surface soil layers may alter stress-strain states and negatively affect the durability of engineering structures located close to railway lines.

This study focuses on the numerical investigation of vibration propagation caused by freight train movement and evaluates how different soil properties influence vibration levels at various distances from the track.

Research Methodology.

The key feature of the approach we are considering is its capacity to effectively address issues by incorporating soil

characteristics. It enables us to simulate large regions within a short period, resulting in a reduction of computation time when dynamically assessing the response at observation points situated between 10 and 100 meters away from railway tracks in the case under analysis.

In this investigation, we compared outcomes obtained for two varieties of soil conditions. The elastic-perfectly plastic Coulomb-Mohr model represents one of the most extensively utilized models of soil behavior. Its primary benefit is that the source data is readily available, which is invariably included in conventional engineering and geological records.

E - represents the modulus of elasticity in MPa, ν - represents Poisson's ratio, φ - represents the angle of internal friction in degrees, C - represents specific adhesion in kPa, and ψ - represents the dilatation angle in degrees.

The Coulomb-Mohr model is used to describe the behavior of soil. Deformation in soil is linear, and it is directly proportional to the stress level σ and varies according to the soil modulus E . Researchers studying soil and structural properties under dynamic loading conditions use elastoplastic and viscoplastic models. The latter provides more accurate results but is more difficult to apply.

A nonlinear soil expansion model takes into account wave propagation and interactions with buildings and structures, yielding wave parameters that differ significantly from those of ideal elastic and nonlinear elastic medium models. The problem involves vibration levels in the ground caused by railway train movement. A model was created using an unpaved foundation 200 m wide, 100 m long, and 50 m deep. The influence of groundwater was not taken into account, and soil characteristics were selected based on Tables 1 and 2 for illustration.

To create the railway track, a design was used that followed the standards for railway track construction, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Drawing construction of the base for a railway train

In accordance with the drawing, a protective layer 1 meter thick and a ballast base 50 centimeters thick are laid on the ground starting from a mark 0 meters above the surface on which the railway track (sleepers and rails) are designed. The movement of a freight train weighing 120 tons with cargo is being studied. The cargo transport is moving at a speed of 100 kilometers per hour. Since the selected area has a length of 100 meters, the vibration acting on the soil base will continue until the freight transport has completely passed through.

To solve this problem, we will use the finite element method. The study area will be divided into **7,875** finite elements. The shapes of these finite elements will be chosen in the form of irregular tetrahedra.

It is believed that the dynamic loads from the train tracks can affect the ground base. In this study, we will consider the action of eight concentrated loads along the z -axis, moving at a certain speed along the y -axis. We will determine the movement and speed of the resulting nodes in the soil, considering the physical and mechanical properties of the material.

In this problem, we will replace the infinite half-space with a finite parallelepiped [3, 4, 5, 6]. Conditions will be set on the faces of the parallelepiped, where the continuation of the medium will be discarded:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_x &= a\rho V_p \dot{u} \\ \tau_{yz} &= b\rho V_s \dot{u} \\ \tau_{zy} &= b\rho V_s \dot{w} \end{aligned} \right\} \left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_y &= a\rho V_p \dot{v} \\ \tau_{xz} &= b\rho V_s \dot{w} \\ \tau_{zx} &= b\rho V_s \dot{u} \end{aligned} \right\} \left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_z &= a\rho V_p \dot{w} \\ \tau_{xy} &= b\rho V_s \dot{u} \\ \tau_{yx} &= b\rho V_s \dot{v} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

the dynamic model of the problem-solving field is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2. A model in which the domain is divided into finite elements.

The fundamental equation that describes the motion of an object under the influence of a force as a function of time can be expressed in the following form:

$$[M]\{\ddot{u}\} + [C]\{\dot{u}\} + [K]\{u\} = \{F\}, \quad (2)$$

The arrangement of [M]- the mass matrix, {u}- the displacement vector, [C] - the damping matrix, which also includes boundary conditions, [K]- the stiffness matrix, and {F}- the load vector are the most important components of the analysis. The {u}- movement, {u[·]}- speed, and {u^{··}}- acceleration of these elements can change over time during dynamic analysis.

In principle, all models can be employed for dynamic analysis regardless of whether the soil is in a dry state or not. The presence or absence of groundwater in the study area during data collection is irrelevant for this purpose. **Plaxis 3D** allows for the resolution of issues related to both the existence and absence of water levels.

The matrix [M] is based on information about the mass of materials, including soil, water, and other components.

For numerical simulation of dynamics, it is important to ensure the stability and accuracy

of calculations. The Newmark numerical integration method helps in this. The properties of soil and other materials are presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Table - 1.

Physical and mechanical properties of materials

Parameter	Unit of measurement	Designation	Sandy loam	Loess-like loam
General properties				
The soil model	–	–	Mohr-Coulomb	Mohr-Coulomb
Type of material behavior	–	–	Drained	Drained
The specific gravity of the soil above the groundwater level	kN/m	γ_{unsa}	16	14,70
The specific gravity of the soil below the groundwater level	kN/m	γ_{sat}	18	16,80
Mechanical parameters				
Young's modulus (constant value)	kN/m	E'_{ref}	60000	95000
The Poisson's ratio	–	ν / ν_{ur}	0.32	0,35
Coupling (permanent)	kN/m	c'_{ref}	6	5,6
Angle of internal friction	°	φ'	22	25
Dilatation angle	°	ψ	1	0

Table - 2.

Features of the ballast layer

Ballast layer	Unit of measurement	Protective layer	Balast
№	1	2	3
The soil model	–	Mohr-Coulomb	Mohr-Coulomb
Type of material behavior	–	Drained	Drained
The specific gravity of the soil above the groundwater level	kN/m^3	22	19
The specific gravity of the soil below the groundwater level	kN/m^3	23	21
Angle of internal friction	φ'	40	35
Dilatation angle	ψ	15	5
Coupling (permanent)	c'_{ref}	30	30
Young's modulus (constant value)	E'_{ref}	55000	50000
The Poisson's ratio	ν / ν_{ur}	0.25	0,3

Physical and mechanical properties of rails and sleepers Table - 3.

		The rail	The sleepers
Specific gravity	[kN/m^3]	78	25
Type of section		User – defined	Defined
Cross sectional area	m^2	0,0077	0,0513
Moment of inertia	I_2	0,00000513	0,000245
	I_3	0,00003005	0,02530
Young's Module	ν	200 000 000	360 000

Results and discussions.

Name	X	Y	Z
Node 12511	10,000	50,000	0,000
Node 11300	1,6137	50,002	0,000
Node 28790	20,222	50,209	0,000
Node 96402	23,617	50,277	0,000
Node 27427	26,022	50,346	0,000
Node 43027	29,788	50,366	0,000
Node 27502	32,655	50,388	0,000
Node 160211	32,322	50,402	0,000
Node 28811	36,209	50,422	0,000
Node 28946	41,206	50,444	0,000
Node 28274	44,133	50,466	0,000
Node 43068	46,999	50,477	0,000
Node 27502	49,266	50,488	0,000
Node 43223	52,273	50,511	0,000
Node 27011	54,640	50,533	0,000
Node 43395	56,477	50,555	0,000
Node 28790	61,322	50,577	0,000
Node 40511	64,200	50,599	0,000
Node 28266	67,227	50,621	0,000
Node 46695	69,044	50,643	0,000
Node 27486	72,811	50,664	0,000
Node 45023	75,648	50,677	0,000
Node 27403	78,544	50,689	0,000
Node 45625	81,466	50,677	0,000
Node 28712	84,388	50,666	0,000
Node 47774	87,500	50,488	0,000
Node 28056	90,622	50,211	0,000
Node 41259	93,223	51,204	0,000
Node 28025	95,625	51,288	0,000
Node 40322	97,922	50,866	0,000
Node 11311	100,000	50,000	0,000

a) The location of the railway track, and the movements of the load in a designated limited area

Fig. 2. Vibration levels in each node of the model being tested

b) Coordinates of the location of the observed points in the area under consideration

c) Moving the points in the direction of the axis

The graphs in Figures 3 and 5 are detailed, showing the fluctuations resulting from the movement of a train on the ground at different distances from a railway track. To analyze the differences in the levels of vibration propagation between the two cases, we analyzed the oscillation rate at several points: 10 m and 100 m from the railway track..

Fig.3. Graph of the time dependence of the rate of fluctuations occurring in sandy loam soil.

Fig.4. Graph of the time dependence of the rate of fluctuations occurring in loess-like loamy soil at various distances.

Fig.5. Graph of the dependence on the time of movement of vibrations, in comparison with sandy loam and loess-loamy soil

Conclusions.

A comparative analysis of the findings obtained from the resolution of issues pertaining to vibration transmission in two distinct types of soil substrates, namely sandy loam and loess-loamy, has been conducted. The investigation reveals that the transmission of vibrations through soil and structures is contingent upon the characteristics of the soil, including its elastic modulus, Poisson's ratio, and density.

Upon comparing the outcomes for the various soil types, it was observed that the velocity of wave transmission varies. The acquired data indicates a second-order velocity of propagation.

When comparing the results to those obtained for sandy loam, it can be seen that the velocity at 20.22 cm will increase by 14.95%, at 49.86 cm it will increase by 39.29%, and at 75.68 cm it will rise by 21.69%, compared to the values obtained for loess-loam. The velocities at these distances will be 71.73%, 12.38%, and 48.37% higher, respectively, than the corresponding values for sandy loam.

At 20.22 meters, the velocity will be 60.64 percent higher; at 49.86 meters, it will only be

5.45 percent higher; and at 75.68 m, it will decrease by 17.2 percent compared to values for sandy loams.

From this, we can conclude that when studying the propagation of vibrations in soils, it is important to consider the actual physical parameters. Based on the results obtained, we can state that the level of vibrations resulting from vehicle traffic largely depends on the properties of the soil. Therefore, when performing calculations, it is critical to take into account both the physical and mechanical properties of the ground.

References

[1] *Il'ichev V.A., Yuldashev S.S., Saidov S.M.* Propagation of vibration from trains in relation to track position //Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering. – 1999. – T. 36. – №. 2. – C. 55-56.

[2] *Lysmer J., Kyhlemeyer L.* Finite Dynamic Model for Infinite Media // Jour Engineering Mechanics Division.ASCE. 1969. Vol. 95.NoEM4.August.P. 859 – 887.

[3] Mirsaidov, M., Boytemirov, M., & Yuldashev, F. (2022). Estimation of the Vibration Waves Level at Different Distances. In *Proceedings of FORM 2021: Construction the Formation of Living Environment* (pp. 207-215). Springer International Publishing.

